

ANNUAL REPORT 2018

DARIAH ERIC:
A research infrastructure
to enhance and support
digitally enabled research
and teaching across the
Arts and Humanities.

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Foreword

The consolidations of 2017 have placed DARIAH in an excellent position to move confidently toward the start of its operational phase in 2019, and the developments of 2018 have been proof of this promise. In particular, the growing clarity around the Strategic Plan 2019-2026 and the launch of the development phase for the long-planned Marketplace stand as evidence of the solidity of the foundation DARIAH now has, and the confidence this lends to the organisation as a whole. These are not the only signs of DARIAH's growing maturity, however: new staff have been recruited to align our operations to our emerging strategy, and transitions where staff have left us have all been orderly and smooth, even in the case of the founding President of our Board of Directors, Laurent Romary, who stepped down in August from the key position he had held with us for so long. We have begun to reach out through the DARIAH beyond Europe events to test our capacity to build our impact internationally. And, of course, we continue to benefit from the excellent inputs to our activities from our long-standing well-springs of good practice and progress beyond the state of the art, namely our national members, our Working Groups, our project collaborators, our Joint Research Committee and our committed staff.

Our environment remains not without challenges, but DARIAH is looking in every case to find the opportunities that lurk behind them. The European Open Science Cloud and the growing emphasis at a policy level on progressing Open Science may have emerged from a very different disciplinary conception of research, but in many ways these movements resonate fundamentally with the core values of the arts and humanities. After all, what is a national archive if not an access point for open research data? What is historical research in the name of understanding one's family tree if not citizen science? Changing the discourse of these movements to recognise the potential and the capacity of the arts and humanities to be major contributors will be a key challenge for us going forward. Similarly, the move toward the development of common KPIs for all ERICs has given us an impetus and opportunity to think deeply about how DARIAH creates value, and how we can document and measure that value.

As we look forward now to 2019, we can see how not just the next year, but the next decade can unfold for DARIAH and its stakeholders to grow in an ever-increasing network of mutual benefit. This is not to say that things won't change in that period, or that DARIAH won't continue to be responsive to its volatile environment, but rather that our solid core will guide us through this process.

Jennifer Edmond

President of the Board of Directors

Jacques Dubucs

President of the General Assembly

DARIAH in a nutshell

The Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH) enhances and supports digitally-enabled research and teaching across the arts and humanities. DARIAH is a research infrastructure of people, expertise, information, knowledge, content, methods, tools and technologies from its member countries. It develops, maintains and operates an infrastructure that sustains researchers in building, analysing and interpreting digital resources. By working with communities of practice, DARIAH brings together individual state-of-the-art digital arts and humanities activities and scales their results to a European level, enabling the transition to Open Science, and beyond to Open Innovation. It preserves, provides access to, and disseminates research that stems from these collaborations and ensures that best practices, methodological and technical standards are followed.

DARIAH was established as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) in August 2014. In 2018, the consortium had 17 Members and 23 Cooperating Partners across 8 non-member countries. DARIAH integrates digital arts and humanities research and activities from across Europe, enabling transnational and transdisciplinary approaches. In particular, it provides value to its members and stakeholders through the validation and sharing of data, services and tools; by providing training and education opportunities; by enabling 'bottom-up' organisation around emerging research needs; and through the exercise of foresight and policy engagement. Through these activities, DARIAH promotes the further development of research methods in the arts and humanities, documenting the state-of-the-art, supporting the preservation and curation of research data with a focus on particular challenges including diversity, provenance, multimedia collections and granularity, and acting as a coordinator and integrator for a diverse community of practice.

The consortium supports the sustainable development of digitally-enabled research in the arts and humanities by building services for researchers working with ICT-based methods. It helps them to further advance their research and ensures the long-term accessibility of their work, thus directly contributing to the understanding of the cultural, economical, social and political life in Europe and beyond. In addition, it offers teaching material as well as teaching opportunities to develop digital research skills.

DARIAH is at the forefront of a changing knowledge discovery market and possesses significant strength in this field through its partners. DARIAH also demonstrates how traditional humanities research skills play a prominent role in the digital age, and how such skills can be deployed in a digital economy setting. The DARIAH vision is that humanities researchers will be able to assess the impact of technology on their work in an informed manner, access the data, tools, services, knowledge and networks they need seamlessly and in contextually rich virtual and human environments and produce excellent, digitally-enabled scholarship that is reusable, visible and sustainable.

Activity highlights 2018

DARIAH Strategy Days 2018

For the second year in a row, members of DARIAH's various governance bodies came together in Berlin for a three-day meeting to reflect on the strategy of the organisation. On the program: a brainstorming session around DARIAH's identity led by external consultants, the review of the strategic actions carried out last year and the first milestones of a 5-year Strategic Plan based on 4 pillars: Training and Education, the Marketplace, Foresight & Policy Work, Building transnational & transdisciplinary research hubs. (see pp. 24-25)

1

January

March

2

GeoHumanities: Creation of a new DARIAH Working Group

The principal objective of the GeoHumanities Working Group is to establish a linked open data registry for a wide range of freely available geospatial datasets and services on the internet, applicable to humanities research. The group – connected to the DARIAH's Virtual Competency Centre for e-Infrastructures – was initiated by a network of researchers in Austria, Belgium, United Kingdom and Finland.

A new Director for DARIAH

Toma Tasovac, Director of the Belgrade Center for Digital Humanities, was appointed by the General Assembly to DARIAH's Board of Directors. Toma's appointment promises to bring to the role an unwavering enthusiasm for the role of the humanities in the contemporary scholarly and political landscapes, as well as a deep knowledge of DARIAH, grounded in years of collaboration. Over the years, he has participated in and led two DARIAH Working Groups, served as National Coordinator for Serbia and Chair of the National Coordinators Committee as well as member of the DARIAH Senior Management Team. (see p. 24)

3

May

4

DARIAH Annual Event 2018

DARIAH set the topic of Open Science as theme of the 2018 Annual Event. It took place on May 22-24 in Paris. With a focus on how to engage the DARIAH community with issues of Open Science in research infrastructures, and how the humanities can adopt new methodologies for open collaboration, the event was a lively meeting point for researchers, Working Groups, DARIAH-related projects and the DARIAH governing bodies to exchange experiences, explore new ideas and discuss future challenges. (see pp. 24-25)

DARIAH Theme 2018: Strategic Service Sustainability for DARIAH

The 2018 edition of the DARIAH Theme focused on the chronic problem of software and tool sustainability in the digital humanities, while also looking forward to the build phase of the DARIAH Marketplace for data, tools and services. Seven promising projects in the area of training, standardisation, datasets, geolocation, annotation services, thesauri and vocabularies were chosen for funding with a total of 75.305 euros.

6

DARIAH welcomes the Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics as a new Cooperating Partner in Switzerland

The SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics joined the strong Swiss consortium of DARIAH Cooperating Partners in November, following upon two applications that were approved earlier this year from the University of Neuchâtel and the École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne. Switzerland belongs to the six DESIR accession countries and is developing a DARIAH-CH consortium in order to support its development toward full DARIAH membership. (see p. 8)

8

September

October

November

December

5

7

9

DARIAH beyond Europe

As part of the Horizon 2020-funded project DESIR, the first two DARIAH beyond Europe events were held on September 13-15 at Stanford University (California) and on October 2-4 at the Library of Congress (Washington DC). Under the topics of "Sustainable Infrastructures for Digital Arts & Humanities: An International DARIAH Exchange" and "Collections as Data: Digital Scholarship in the Arts and Humanities", the two conferences brought together digital humanists from the US and Europe to exchange knowledge and experience, initiate collaborations and discuss the state of play across the two continents. (see pp. 11-12)

Two new members of the Scientific Board

During its November meeting, DARIAH's General Assembly elected Sarah Kenderdine, Professor of Digital Museology at the École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL), and Arianna Betti, Professor (Chair) of Philosophy of Language at the University of Amsterdam, as new members of the Scientific Board succeeding Andrew Prescott and Manfred Thaller. (see p. 24)

Lexical Data Masterclass 2018

With the support of the French Ministry for Research, Higher Education and Innovation, DARIAH organised its second Lexical Data Masterclass. This event brought together advanced trainees and experts in Berlin to share experiences, methods and techniques for the creation, management and use of lexical data. (see p. 17)

1. Nurturing and expanding DARIAH's network

a. The DARIAH Community in 2018

DARIAH should be a stepping stone to better work ... open, available, and tuned to the community's needs.

– Jennifer Edmond, September 2018

The very nature of the DARIAH community makes any attempt to define its scope and perimeter at least complex. If the core of the organisation is composed of a handful of persons, its ramifications spread to an ever-widening community of individuals and institutions that organise themselves at both national and European levels. Furthermore, the nature of the DARIAH “user” adds further complexity to the architecture of the community: most DARIAH users are at the same time the creators of DARIAH, through their participation in Working Groups and projects,

through their generation of in kind contributions and local influence. The arts and humanities research base in Europe has been estimated to encompass more than 500.000 individuals in research, teaching and cultural heritage. Every one of these is a potential DARIAH user, but the distributed nature of our organisation means that often, there is one or more degrees of separation from the central offices. However, as illustrated with the figure below, DARIAH's sphere of influence is large and each of these layers contributes to its unique strength.

Figure: Size of the DARIAH community, 2018

b. Working Groups

Currently, DARIAH hosts 22 Working Groups (WGs), which cover a wide spectrum of disciplines and collaborations between research and service institutions. Working Groups remain at the heart of DARIAH. With their roots in transnational communities of practice, they self-organise under the DARIAH umbrella to foster innovative scholarly practices and to provide the infrastructure to support them.

2018 saw three new Working Groups launch their activities. The first one, the **WG Digital Numismatics**, aims at developing and demonstrating the availability and benefits of Linked Open Data, and to assemble best practices in their application, within the numismatic community and in related disciplines. It addresses research questions in the humanities and enhances interoperability, thus facilitating the sharing and reuse of large digital datasets across domains.

The **WG Music and Artificial Intelligence (AIM)** is composed of academic researchers, industry practitioners and government institutions with a deep interest in strengthening all fronts of interaction between Music and Artificial Intelligence. The goal of AIM is to connect and bring together individuals, groups and institutions that do research and work around the different aspects of Music and AI.

The **WG Practice of Digital Urban Heritage (UGiDiSH)** counts a very rich network of participants and collaborators. The Working Group objective is to create a network of stakeholders for transnational collaboration between cities facing challenges such as economic difficulties, gentrification and migration. It aims at revisiting the notion of cultural values and built heritage, towards inclusive, innovative and reflective societies – for example, in conflict spaces, where the common past and heritage can be established as a bridge for peace. Responding to these pressing challenges can only be achieved through transnational collaboration as the challenges are complex and ill-defined and thus cannot be dealt with at a local scale.

Focus on the Chairs of the AIM Working Group

The AI and Music (AIM) DARIAH Working Group is co-chaired by Albert Meroño-Peñuela (Knowledge Representation & Reasoning, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam; Amsterdam, The Netherlands) and Enrico Daga (Knowledge Media Institute, The Open University; Milton Keynes, United Kingdom). Albert holds a PhD from the Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, a Master of Informatics Engineering from Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (FIB-UPC) and has done research at the Autonomous University of Barcelona (UAB). His research interests include Linked Open Data, Government and Statistical data, Artificial Intelligence and Digital Humanities. Enrico holds a PhD from the Open University, a degree on Music and Performing Arts (University RomaTRE) and he is founder of the WHiSe Workshop on Humanities in the Semantic Web.

"We share the enthusiasm for AI, Knowledge Graphs, and Music and we are currently working on setting a research agenda for Music Knowledge Graphs that can help researchers, technology firms and end users to access musical knowledge more effectively" explains Albert. "In fact one of the main objectives of AIM is to strengthen all fronts of advocacy at the intersection of Music and Artificial Intelligence. In order to do this, we address the outreach needs of universities, industry and institutions by creating a map of communities around AI and Music and providing them with various communication and exchange means".

"Our WG made its first contact with another DARIAH Working Group, Community Engagement (Eliza Papaki and Vicky Garnett) in June 2018 at the Digital Humanities Benelux conference in Amsterdam, which was ideal for a new WG within VCC1. More recently, in February 2019, AIM participated in its first DARIAH WG community call, from which we learned potential collaborations with the Thesaurus Maintenance WG; and we are expecting to have our first WG meeting in the upcoming DARIAH 2019 conference in Warsaw" adds Enrico. "The WG is also busy in preparing a series of webinars, in which we expect to gather and exchange knowledge about the composition of the various AI&Music communities around the world".

c. DARIAH at the national level

The richness and dynamism of the DARIAH consortium lies first and foremost in the diversity and plurality of its member countries. It is they who every day through their actions, projects and influence make DARIAH a key infrastructure in the field of the arts and humanities. National Members meet and work through the National Coordinators Committee (NCC) that gathers regularly either virtually or face to face to reflect on and coordinate the actions of its members. In 2018, they worked more specifically on a synthesis of national roadmaps and contributed to the strategic reflection of DARIAH from a national perspective. Furthermore, the NCC extended their commitment to helping grow the DARIAH membership by opening their meetings to the 6 countries preparing for accession under the DESIR project (see next section).

Many of these candidate countries are already represented within DARIAH by institutions that participate as Cooperating Partners. In 2018, DARIAH had a total of 23 Cooperating Partners, welcoming 3 new ones from Switzerland in the course of the year:

- University of Neuchâtel
- École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL)
- Swiss Institute for Bioinformatics

National DARIAH nodes build their local and regional research contexts in a variety of ways, with rich programmes of events and initiatives. Two nodes that have made particular progress in 2018 were Croatia and the Netherlands, their stories are featured below.

Focus on CLARIAH-NL

With an atypical background in business economics, IT entrepreneurship and medieval history, Gertjan Filarski is currently working as CTO of CLARIAH (Common Lab Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities) and director of Digital Infrastructure for the Humanities Cluster of the KNAW (Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences). He also became the DARIAH National Coordinator for the Netherlands in May 2018.

Could you introduce us to the role and work of CLARIAH?

Historically, the Dutch part of the European infrastructures CLARIN and DARIAH were run as two separate projects from 2009 to 2013. Then, the Dutch Research Council (NWO) told us that they would only consider an application from the humanities if we combined the two infrastructures; that was the beginning of CLARIAH. We first received seed money (CLARIAH-SEED) with which we build a number of pilots that led to the four-year project CLARIAH-CORE. Started in 2014, its goal was to develop a good, useful, sustainable and user-friendly infrastructure for the humanities. We applied for a second round which was awarded at the end of 2018 and honored with M€ 13.8. This project, CLARIAH-PLUS (2019-2024), will allow us to continue and extend the actions started in CORE.

At CLARIAH CORE, we cover 3 domains or work packages (WP): linguistics, socio-economical history and media studies. that correspond to the 3 basic data types we support: text, structured data and audio & video. During CLARIAH-CORE, we were very focus on tool building but the link between the different infrastructures already build or initiated remained loose. In CLARIAH-PLUS we have added a new WP that focusses on the semantic interpretation of text, which corresponds with the domains of history and literary studies. Moreover, CLARIAH PLUS aims to connect the infrastructures in a much-concerted way. The first step is to work on the ground layer, the hardware that powers those tools: resource allocation, processing power, memory, storage, network connections. On top of that we start to implement a number of fundamental pieces of software needed by the entire infrastructure: Identification, Authentication and Authorization (IAA), persistent identification, sustainable storage, etc.

We already see that a number of generic services like the knowledge graph or the IAA are now being used by other externally funded projects or used by research groups across the country. In the past when research projects involved in DH infrastructure were funded, most of them allocated a part of their budget to build e.g. sustainable storage...Instead of doing that they spend their funding on actual research and use our services for the rest. That is the core mission of CLARIAH.

What would you consider to be the 3 most significant events of 2018 for CLARIAH?

1. CLARIAH-PLUS project has been granted with M€ 13.8

On April 11, 2018, the minister of Education, Culture and Science, Ingrid van Engelshoven, officially announced the allocation € 13.8 million on behalf of the NWO to the CLARIAH-PLUS project within the framework of the National Roadmap for Large-Scale Scientific Infrastructures. As mentioned earlier, thanks to this allocation, we will be able to consolidate and expand the infrastructure for the next five years.

2. The Amsterdam Time Machine (ATM)

In December, the board of CLARIAH has awarded the ATM project with a grant of € 251.000. Thanks to this grant, the geo-infrastructure HisGIS of the Fryske Akademy will become available to ATM and the general CLARIAH-infrastructure, which means that any humanities researcher will have complete access to all data and tools. Part of the grant will also be used to develop three use cases, one in linguistics, one in social & economic history and one in media studies, which will demonstrate the possibilities of the CLARIAH-infrastructure. The project connects the Amsterdam cultural heritage institutions in AdamNet with the creative industry, the municipality of Amsterdam and social sciences and humanities researchers.

3. The NEWSGAC project

This project studies how genres in newspapers and television news can be detected automatically using machine learning in a transparent manner. It means that we open the "black box" of machine learning by comparing, predicting and visualizing the effects of applying various algorithms on heterogeneous data. This enables scholars to do large-scale analyses of (historic) texts and other media types as well as critically evaluate the methodological effects of various machine learning approaches.

How would you personally define the role of National Coordinator (NC)?

I think the most important thing for me, as NC for the Netherlands, is to be the bridge with CLARIAH. As CTO, I am in the board of CLARIAH which also includes Jan Odjik, the national coordinator of CLARIN. Given the past in the Netherlands the board has a natural tendency to focus more on CLARIN. I find really important to bring up the DARIAH inputs as well into the Board. However, I am quite new in my role as NC and I still find it difficult to find the right things in DARIAH to bring to the attention of the Board. I still lack experience to express myself on the role of NC in general but I hope that the influence of NCs within DARIAH will be strong and that their voices will be heard.

Focus on DARIAH-HR

How would you describe the structure and work of DARIAH-HR (DARIAH in Croatia)?

DARIAH-HR is a network of 33 national institutions and 5 associate institutions from Bosnia and Herzegovina and Macedonia. Despite the fact that DARIAH-HR has not been granted any funding yet, we are very active and working with in-kind contributions of individuals and institutions.

The main focus of the DARIAH-HR activities is the further development of a cooperation between the GLAM, IT and the scientific sector as well as the establishment of cooperation between the Ministry of Science and Education and the Ministry of Culture on the planning and financing of a national DH infrastructure. We have been also fostering cooperation in regional frameworks, as a center of a DARIAH Western Balkan Hub, through some DH projects and meetings. Regarding wider international cooperation and DARIAH-EU related objectives, our efforts focus on establishing new Working Groups covering areas that are not sufficiently represented in DARIAH. Three examples of this would be: WG on Ethics and Legality (already established at the end of 2017); WG on Theater Studies and Theatralia Digitization, initiated by University of Osijek; WG Art, Art History and Technology initiated by the Institute of the Art history (in preparatory phase).

In 2019, we are planning to employ a small team of researchers to help with DH and DARIAH related issues and then reorganize and improve the way our DARIAH-HR national consortium is functioning.

DARIAH-HR organised numerous events in 2018, what were the highlights of the year?

In 2018, we organised at least 15 events, from Working Group workshops to international conferences. Let me highlight few of these:

1. *Forum for the Application and Establishment of a DARIAH Working Group on Theater Studies and Theatralia Digitisation, Osijek, 23-24 March 2018*

This two-day event and initiative evoked an interest not only in Croatia but also in Austria, Bulgaria, Denmark, Germany, Hungary, Poland, Rumania, Serbia and in the United Kingdom. The event gathered over one hundred domestic and foreign experts in Theater Studies and practitioners from the DARIAH member countries to debate on the necessary elements for the application and establishment of the aforementioned Working Group, which is thematically unique within DARIAH.

2. *DARIAH Day Zagreb 2018, organised in the context of the international conference Methods, Practices and Epistemologies of Digital Art History, Zagreb 12-14 November 2018*

This conference has been one of the most important DH conference with participants from all over the world that emphasized the achievements, needs and problems of the digital art history field. The DARIAH Day Zagreb 2018, which was organised on the third day of the conference, presented a DARIAH-HR initiative for the establishment of an Art, Art History & Technology Working Group, aiming to bring together artists, art historians, designers, media theorists, IT specialists and other professionals involved with new digital media and communication technologies.

3. *4 regional workshops have been organized in the context of the project Cooperation framework of digital infrastructure in the region - opportunities and needs in case of material concerning famous people in science and culture (DARIAH Theme 2017, 1 October 2017-30 November 2018)*

This project has strengthened cooperation with partners from the DARIAH Western Balkan Hub and from Slovenia. The undertaken work included testing the interoperability of digital repositories from different institutions and different countries by analysing ways of harvesting material and creating a single metadata search approach, standardization of digital object cataloguing methods and gathering information on different copyright law stipulations in the region.

How would you personally define the role of National Coordinator?

National Coordinators act as DARIAH ambassadors, as a glue on a national level. Their role is to act as a link between institutions and individuals in the area of Digital Humanities and Art, from universities and research institutions to the whole GLAM sector. National Coordinators strive to recognise the needs and opportunities for the whole community, motivate associates to be proactive, keep them informed about DH events, projects and initiatives in the rest of Europe and the world, through national communication channels, organise DARIAH related events, roundtables, conferences, workshops etc. At the same time, National Coordinators regularly communicate the current situation and needs of their national DH community to the Ministry of Science and Education. You can think of National Coordinators as some sort of a matchmaker serving between national institutions and individuals and those from other DARIAH countries who share the same research interest for future collaborations.

d. On the road to DARIAH membership

As a pan-European research infrastructure, DARIAH is always open and ready to support new countries working towards becoming DARIAH members. The Horizon 2020-funded project DESIR (DARIAH ERIC Sustainability Refined) features participation from six countries not yet members of DARIAH: Czech Republic, Finland, Israel, Spain, Switzerland and the United Kingdom. The stated objective for these countries is to foster mutually beneficial relationships, showcase the infrastructure and start building national consortia in these countries, with the ultimate goal of achieving full membership in DARIAH. A key element of this task is the organisation of dedicated workshops in each of the candidate countries in order to introduce them to the DARIAH infrastructure and related services and to develop methodological research skills.

In April 2018, two events took place. The University of Glasgow held a workshop to discuss EU and UK research collaboration in the Digital Humanities. The workshop was high-level, practice-focused and aimed at developing a strategy to assess the purpose and the means by which the UK might join DARIAH. Representatives from DARIAH, CLARIN, RLUK (Research Libraries UK) and AHRC (Arts and Humanities Research Council) as well as participants from research institutions such as Oxford University, University of Exeter, Glasgow University, University of York, University of London and King's College London, participated in this workshop.

Later that month, Prague hosted the DARIAH-CZ Workshop on Digital Humanities with the aim of introducing DARIAH and increasing its visibility in the Czech Republic to obtain stronger support towards DARIAH membership. The workshop was built over four sessions: the first two introduced DARIAH and its architecture, the DESIR project, the DARIAH Central European Hub and European initiatives in the domain of Digital Humanities. Talks were given by Frank Fischer, Director of DARIAH-EU, Elisabeth Burr, President of the European Association for Digital Humanities, Karlheinz Mörth, from the Academy of Sciences in Vienna, Jakub Szprot, National Coordinator of DARIAH Poland, Gábor Palkó from Petőfi Literary Museum in Budapest and Martin Lhotak, Deputy Director of the Library of the Czech Academy of Sciences. There was a presentation of the roadmap of large research infrastructures at the national level while various DH tools and research projects were also showcased. A total of 65 participants attended the event and, among them, partners of DARIAH-CZ and LINDAT/CLARIN consortia,

researchers, librarians, DH projects managers and DARIAH-EU representatives.

In September, the University of Helsinki and HELDIG Centre for Digital Humanities hosted a DARIAH-FI meeting in Helsinki. This workshop was the occasion to present the benefits of joining DARIAH, but at the same time to provide an overview of the Finnish humanities landscape from the perspective of research infrastructures. The meeting registered the presence of Finnish nodes of CLARIN and CESSDA, the Academy of Finland and several Finnish universities that are interested in taking part in the future consortium. Several sessions were facilitated by Jennifer Edmond, Director of DARIAH-EU, who guided the group in a discussion on their national priorities, strengths and possible points of synergy with other DARIAH countries.

In October, Israel organised a DESIR workshop at the University of Haifa Library as part of the "Digital Humanities Month". The responses to the workshop were very positive and there was a very good turnout of participants from representatives of institutions, including the National Library and research institutes, librarians, researchers and university officials.

Workshop Digital Infrastructures in Spain, Madrid, October 2018

DARIAH-CH Workshop, University of Neuchâtel, Switzerland, November 2018

Towards the end of the year, two more high-profile events took place in Spain and Switzerland. In October, the National Distance Education University (UNED) and its Center on Innovation and Digital Humanities hosted a workshop on *Digital Infrastructures in Spain* to discuss opportunities for collaboration in the area of infrastructures for current Spanish national projects. Finally, the University of Neuchâtel organised a DARIAH-CH workshop in November which registered the presence, among others, of representatives from the State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation, the Swiss Academy of Humanities and Social Sciences as well as DH researchers of major Universities in Switzerland. The workshop was structured around 5 sessions in which various key issues for scholars in the Digital Humanities were addressed, such as preservation, interoperability, data management or funding. Furthermore, the event was an opportunity to reflect on the development of Digital Humanities in Switzerland and how this could be further supported.

e. DARIAH beyond Europe

In addition to engaging with new members from within Europe, another initiative of the DESIR project has been to explore the potential benefit of building key partnerships with leading institutions from outside Europe. To this end, the project included plans for three international workshops, two of which were held in 2018.

The first event took place at **Stanford University, California, USA**, in September and focussed on the topic of *Sustainable Infrastructures in the Digital Arts and Humanities*. The conference highlighted ongoing work in DARIAH such as the Marketplace and Working Groups activities, and how these projects and initiatives could potentially intersect with DH initiatives in North America, particularly on the West Coast.

The three-day event was structured along two main tracks. Four different knowledge exchange sessions on the topics of Corpus Management, Text and Image Analysis, GeoHumanities, and Music, Theater and Sound Studies, gave participants the opportunity to present the state-of-the-art both on the European and the USA sides and exchange their experiences.

In parallel, the event hosted three keynote speakers. The opening keynote speaker, Quinn Dombrowski, Digital Humanist and Academic Technology Specialist at Stanford University, talked about *Cowboys and Consortia: Thoughts on DH Infrastructure*. Quinn shared some thoughts on recent DH infrastructural efforts in the United States, successes and failures, and reflected on the shifts in scholarship, partnership and funding priorities that might support a turn towards a meaningful DH infrastructure in the United States. In the second keynote, Ge Wang, Stanford Professor of Music and founder of the Stanford Laptop Orchestra (SLOrk), presented his book *Artful Design: Technology in Search of the Sublime*, inviting the audience to both embrace and confront technology, not purely as a means to an end, but in its potential to enrich life. Finally, Mark Algee-Hewitt, with his keynote on *Humanities, Augmented: Ecologies of digital research practices*, presented Digital Humanities as augmented humanities, offering suggestions for a set of sustainable research practices.

Stanford University hosted the first DARIAH beyond Europe event in September 2018

The Bender Room hosted the DARIAH beyond Europe presentations in Stanford, USA

The event was followed in October by a workshop held in **Washington D.C., USA**. The main theme of the workshop was *Collections as Data*, which signalled the intention to explore best practices for developing researcher engagement with digital collections, particularly through computationally-driven research. Hosted by the **Library of Congress (LoC)**, it brought together digital humanists from the US East Coast and Europe to exchange ideas and discuss the state of play on the two continents. Again, the event was structured around knowledge exchange sessions, on Digital Newspapers & Text Analysis, Infrastructural Challenges for Public Humanities and Using Web Archives in Humanities Research. Two keynotes were delivered by Jason Rhody, Program Director of Digital Culture at the Social Science Research Council (SSRC), and jointly by Laurie Allen and Stewart Varner, respectively Assistant Director for Digital Scholarship at the University of Pennsylvania Libraries and Managing Director of the Price Lab for Digital Humanities at the University of Pennsylvania.

Through these two events, opportunities for collaboration emerged in particular in the context of connecting international scholars with existing DARIAH Working Groups. Furthermore, US participants were offered the opportunity to explore DARIAH tools and provide input to our plans for the Open SSH Marketplace. The events have also encouraged us to rethink the place of the Cooperating Partner in DARIAH as a possible mechanism for sustaining engagement with institutional partners from all over the world.

The Library of Congress hosted the second DARIAH beyond Europe event in October 2018

In Stanford, USA (Ltr): Quinn Dombrowski, Anthony Caldwell, Zoe Borovsky, Alix Keener, Joke Daems

f. DARIAH and the EOSC

One of the most significant developments in the European research policy landscape in recent years has been the emergence of the European Open Science Cloud, or EOSC. The vision of the EOSC is to make a significant proportion of the research data in Europe open, reusable and discoverable, through a set of coordinated services and policies. In 2018, that vision finally became a reality, and DARIAH representatives attended the festive launch under the Austrian presidency of the Council of the European Union.

For the DARIAH community, the development of the EOSC presents an opportunity to make visible the services and tools that already exist, even if that means facing a number of substantive barriers to open data in the arts and humanities, such as:

- The traditional ownership of humanities research data as shared between the researchers exploring them and the cultural heritage institutions or publishers charged with preserving and promoting them,
- the hybrid nature of humanities research data, with many elements stubbornly analogue, and an enduring role preserved for tacit and embodied forms of knowledge,
- the individualised nature of research processes, and in particular of intermediate forms of output, which may manifest as paradata, annotation, or other kinds of unstructured notes and comments,
- and the lack of satisfaction among researchers with the term 'data' as precise enough to adequately describe the inputs or outputs of human-centred research.

The DARIAH approach to fostering this integration operates across our range of activity areas. First of all, from a policy perspective, DARIAH Director Jennifer Edmond has been a member of the Open Science Policy Platform since 2016. This body consists of 25 representatives of major stakeholders in the transition to Open Science, from publishers to university and funder associations to e-infrastructures such as GÉANT and EGI. The group was convened by the European Commission to translate expert advice on the progress towards Open Science into practical stakeholder commitments, and it has produced a number of influential policy statements, such as its combined recommendations, OSPP-REC.

Being increasingly recognized as a voice of the arts and humanities perspectives at the European-level, in 2018, DARIAH participated in a range of high-level consultations including the Data Stewardship Skills, the FAIR Data Action Plan or the EU Open Science Monitor. This work is supplemented by the activities of the DARIAH Open Science Officer, Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra, who was appointed in March 2018. She not only represents DARIAH and its stakeholders at a wide range of meetings, such as the Open Humanities conference at the University of Barcelona in July, the OpenUP conference in Brussels in September and the OpenCon in Toronto, Canada, in November, but she is also responsible for progressing internal policy initiatives, such as the Data Reuse Charter, and offering advice and training for researchers new to Open Science.

Finally, DARIAH launched its perhaps most ambitious response to the development of the EOSC in 2018 with the capture of significant funding through the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) project to build the SSH Open Marketplace. DARIAH is one of the five ERICs in SSH involved in this project, along with CLARIN, SHARE, ESS, and CESSDA (who is leading the project). Through this funding and collaborative work of the five linked DARIAH partners in Austria, France, Germany and Poland, DARIAH will build a transformational resource for the arts, humanities and social sciences, aligned with the EOSC but also with the requirements of these research communities.

These challenges are not unique to the arts and humanities, but they are particularly pronounced in these disciplines, a factor that has often caused the DARIAH community to be viewed as needlessly resistant to the development of Open Science. To address this gap and the underlying issues, DARIAH is implementing a global strategy to ensure that DARIAH researchers are fully able to take advantage of the benefits of Open Science, and in particular of the EOSC.

g. DARIAH collaborations

DARIAH's embedding into its environment of similar and distinct organisations made significant progress in 2018, as our growing confidence of our mission and identity made us able to reach out across boundaries to engage as leading partners in strong and mutually beneficial bilateral and group initiatives. This has taken place on many levels:

i. CLARIN ERIC

One of the relationships we continued to foster in 2018 has been the growing close cooperation with our fellow ERIC, CLARIN. Although the two organisations have very different structures and service models, the overlap in our communities make this a natural partnership that we have continued to build on since the launch of our joint Course Registry in 2017. Members of the leadership of the two organisations met in March, June and September of 2018, and a number of fruitful areas for collaboration were defined, including training and education, ethical and legal issues and communications. The two ERICs also agreed to an exchange of best practices in terms of the management and sustainability of ERICs, and laid the groundwork for collaborating on a number of events and exchanges in 2019.

ii. HERA

DARIAH Director Jennifer Edmond was invited, along with her CLARIN counterpart Darja Fišer, to present to the meeting of the Humanities in the European Research Area (HERA) consortium in January 2018. HERA brings together a majority of the research funding agencies active in supporting the arts and humanities across Europe, and the members were very interested to learn more about how DARIAH and CLARIN build collaborative research infrastructure relevant to the HERA community. A particular point of shared interest was found in the question of how to sustain the outputs of digital humanities research projects, and the three organisations agreed to seek

shared policies and protocols to promote more robust and reusable project outputs in the future.

iii. The ERIC Forum

Under the impulse of the European Commission, the research infrastructures with an ERIC legal contract are working towards responding to common challenges. Out of this impetus to develop a common voice and share knowledge more systematically, the 23 partners of the previously informal ERIC Forum applied for and were granted 1,5 million euros to build more structured and formal collaboration and coordination while integrating more ERICs.

iv. The EURISE Network

The EURISE Network has been formed by the three Social Sciences and Humanities ERICs, CESSDA, CLARIN & DARIAH, to create an umbrella under which research infrastructures meet research software engineers. It was created following a DESIR workshop on Software Sustainability at the end of 2017. This year was the opportunity to develop the network, strengthen the links between its members and make it more visible. The EURISE Network was presented at two conferences: the DI4R 2018 in Lisbon and the 2018 IEEE 14th International Conference on e-Science. One of its main current outputs is the Technical Reference, a collection of basic guidelines and references for development and maintenance of infrastructure services, which was designed on top of work done by the community.

2. Connecting, informing, creating and fostering

a. Connecting communities

i. Annual Event 2018

The DARIAH Annual Event 2018, which was held on May 22-24 at the Chalet de la Porte Jaune in Paris, was a lively meeting point for researchers, Working Groups, DARIAH related projects and the DARIAH governing bodies to exchange experiences, present progress, explore new ideas and discuss future challenges. DARIAH decided to set *Open Science* as the theme of the 2018 Annual Event with the aim of engaging the DARIAH community in discussions on how we deal with issues of Open Science in research infrastructures, and how the humanities can adopt new methodologies for open collaboration.

The 150 attendees of the 2018 edition were given the opportunity to enjoy **two keynote lectures on Open Science** given respectively by Dr. Jon Tennant and Prof. Teresa Scassa. The former invited scholars to kick-start a new culture of open scientific practices that are by no means distinct from doing high quality research in a transparent and accessible manner. He also tackled some of the current barriers to Open Science: fear, power and competition driving inertia. The closing keynote provided by Prof. Teresa Scassa addressed the role of intellectual property rights in the creation and advancement of scholarly knowledge. She touched upon both valid and perceived tensions between Open Science and restrictions in intellectual property rights and showcased how IPR issues can in some cases foster innovation.

Annual Event 2018, Paris, France, May 2018

Panel of directors, Annual Event 2018

Keynote speech by Dr. Jon Tennant, Annual Event 2018

Keynote speech by Prof. Teresa Scassa, Annual Event 2018

DH Course Registry Metadatathon, Annual Event 2018

Posters Marketplace, Annual Event 2018

The DARIAH Annual Event attendees participated in many workshops such as:

- **Promoting Open Scholarship in DH: Reasons and Tools for Open Licensing** (organized by the WG ELDAH)

This workshop provided a) a very basic introduction to legal terms and issues regarding copyright and publication, b) explained how open licenses work and how they can help in making our work more visible and accessible, and c) showcased some of the most prominent open licensing tools aimed at scholars with no legal background.

- **DH Course Registry Metadatathon** (organized by WG DH Course Registry)

The DH Course Registry is a platform that allows users to access a database containing, at this point, over 140 courses and training events. Participants in the Metadatathon had the opportunity to work "hands-on" with the system and to enter the metadata for their own course – creating more visibility for each individual initiative and adding a puzzle piece to the teaching and training landscape of DH.

- **DH in Ten Years From Now. PARTHENOS 'Foresight Study Workshop'** (organized by the PARTHENOS Project)

This session was one of a series of structured, interactive workshops organised by the PARTHENOS project team, aimed at obtaining input and feedback from a range of stakeholders regarding current and future developments in their particular regions, disciplines and sectors. The foresight study will feed into strategic R&D thinking within the EC, other funding bodies and research organisations.

- **Open Peer Review hands on: alternative methods of evaluation in scholarly publishing** (organized by Foster and OpenUp)

This workshop aimed at a) assessing existing and evolving methods and functions of alternative peer review mechanisms, b) breaking down peer review into the basic processes to identify the benefits and challenges, and c) identifying questions and issues that need further investigation. Group discussions also focussed on sustainability, long-term availability of alternative review tools, and their uptake by researchers and the incorporation of these methods into institutional, national, funders' and publishers' policies.

ii. Code Sprint in Berlin

Technology is a crucial area for a state-of-the-art research infrastructure. In this respect, DARIAH profited in 2018 via the network of its DESIR project, from the unique expertise of three technology partners – Interdisciplinary Centre for Mathematical and Computational Modelling (ICM) from the University of Warsaw, the Institut National de Recherche en Informatique et en Automatique (INRIA) and LR3S Research Center of the University of Hannover. In particular, these partners are working with DARIAH towards the development of concepts and demonstrators in three areas of central importance for DARIAH's long-term sustainability: entity-based search, scholarly content management, visualisation and text analytic services. The project will deliver at least three demonstrators or concepts for services or applications by the end of the DESIR project in December 2019.

In order to ensure momentum for this work, the Göttingen State and University Library organised a Code Sprint on the topic of bibliographic metadata. The Code Sprint took place from 31 July to 2 August at the Institute of Library and Information Science of the Humboldt University of Berlin. The event was open to everyone interested in programming for Digital Humanities use cases and was announced through DARIAH's and other channels. The organisation of the Code Sprint was well received by the Digital Humanities community: 33 participants with different backgrounds, the majority of them unaffiliated to the DARIAH community, attended the three-day event. The workshop opened with a keynote from Prof. Ralf Schenkel of Trier University and affiliated with the Digital Bibliography and Library Project (DBLP). The work was articulated around 4 different tracks:

- Track A: Extraction of bibliographical data and citations from PDF applying GROBID,
- Track B: Import and export of bibliographical data from BibSonomy and ingest in managed collections,
- Track C: Visualisation of processed data with added dimensions for journals, topics, or dependency graphs,
- Track D: Securing Online Services in the DARIAH AAI using SAML/Shibboleth.

The results were made openly available on the DESIR CodeSprint Github repository for anyone to reuse. Based on the success of this event, the DESIR project will organise a second such Code Sprint in the second half of 2019.

iii. From Àbèsàbèsì to XPath: the Lexical Data Masterclass 2018

The 2018 edition of the Lexical Data Masterclass took place in Berlin, on December 3-7, at the Berlin Brandenburg Academy of Sciences (BBAW). Co-organized by DARIAH, the BBAW, Inria and the Belgrade Center for Digital Humanities, with the support of the French Ministry for Research, Higher Education and Innovation, CLARIN and the European Lexicographic Infrastructure (ELEXIS), this second Lexical Data Masterclass brought together advanced trainees and experts to share experiences, methods and techniques for the creation, management and use of lexical data.

The masterclass covered a number of topics ranging from general models for lexical content and TEI-based representation of lexical data to working efficiently with XML editors. By hosting different sessions, the aim was to provide participants the opportunity to touch upon multiple different topics, consult with experts on their own dictionary projects and get to know and test TEI Lex-0, a newly proposed baseline encoding for lexicographic data.

The projects presented during the masterclass came under six main topics: specialized dictionaries; from PDF to TEI using GROBID dictionary; update of the Standards Survival Kit; TEI-based dictionary projects; language documentation projects; and from legacy formats and databases to TEI.

DESIR Code Sprint, Berlin, Germany, July/August 2018

The Lexical Data Masterclass 2018, Berlin, Germany, December 2018

iv. Working Groups community calls

In August 2018, the CIO team established a new mechanism to support transnational research in DARIAH, namely the Working Groups community calls.

Inspiration for the community calls format came from Open Access and global/dispersed communities such as Greenpeace and OpenCon. Community calls are a way to engage with stakeholders that work in dispersed or virtual teams (like the DARIAH WGs) and in the DARIAH context they are open to all Working Group chairs. Their aim is to facilitate exchange between the DARIAH WGs on topics in which they have a common interest, or that might form a basis for future collaboration. The calls were instigated in response to feedback received during the WG Exchange Meeting at the Annual Event in Paris, in which WG Chairs called for more support and integration. The community calls are therefore envisioned as a “virtual” continuation of the “live” WG Exchange Meetings that take place each year and where the WGs members have the chance to meet each other in person.

The first community call, chaired by Costis Dallas of the WG DiMPO (Digital Methods and Practises Observatory), took place on 30 August and focussed on practical and conceptual questions about their upcoming survey on scholarly practices and digital needs of Humanities researchers.

b. Creating tools and services for the community

i. PARTHENOS training suite

As a part of its commitment to providing training materials to inform new generations of digital humanists (whatever their career stage), DARIAH staff and community members have been working with partner research infrastructures through the PARTHENOS project to produce targeted, tailored, open educational resources. In 2018, the platform’s already popular units on introducing research infrastructure, the management of large scale research challenges and collaboration in the Digital Humanities, were supplemented by two major additions on managing data in an open humanities context and taking first steps toward the use of formal ontologies like CIDOC-CRM in humanities work. With both of these releases complete, the team has been turning their efforts to developing further releases planned for 2019, including citizen science and formulating humanities research questions in a data-driven context.

ii. Helpdesk

Another tangible benefit of the DESIR project is the Helpdesk, which is based on the already existing system used by DARIAH-DE. This centralised point for accessing information about DARIAH and its services has been designed to strengthen and accelerate communications with external stakeholders, project the DARIAH brand outward and increase user satisfaction with DARIAH as an organisation. Based on a review of over 500 emails received through the info@dariah.eu email address, the Helpdesk now provides streamlined access to existing information and DARIAH experts across the following categories: Education and Training; Join DARIAH; Open Science; Tools and services; Working Groups; General and technical issues. The DARIAH Helpdesk has its dedicated space on the website and is operational since the end of December 2018.

iii. Interoperability plugins with NERD and ISIDORE

As described in the Annual Report 2017, helping Digital Humanities scholars to find the tools and methods that are most relevant to their work is a core mission of the OpenMethods metablog. In 2018, we enhanced the functionality of the platform by implementing plugins to deliver interoperability with the entity recognition NERD service and the research discovery platform ISIDORE, thereby increasing the visibility and discoverability of our content.

The NERD plugin

The NERD is a service that recognizes and disambiguates named entities, like people, places and dates. This plugin allows integration of the NERD service with the OpenMethods WordPress environment. As a form of content enrichment, the plugin automatically creates tags from the named entities offered by NERD, based on the full text of the original article that has been republished on OpenMethods. The tags, in return, are used to propose extra information coming from Wikipedia and Wikidata. These tags contribute to better discoverability and searchability of content on OpenMethods and add extra contextual layers to our content.

The Rich meta in RDFa plugin

A second new plugin increases the findability of our content on other discovery platforms via Dublin Core metadata enrichments in RDFa within the HTML header of each post. This content is currently being harvested by ISIDORE, an indexing and search service for the humanities and social sciences that serves as a single entry point for a wide range of open SSH resources, such as data, publications and other materials.

The ISIDORE Suggestion plugin

We also integrated a third plugin developed by the ISIDORE team at Huma-Num (DARIAH-FR): it adds an additional discovery layer by providing recommendations of similar content from other OpenMethods posts.

c. Supporting our community to adopt Open Science

Bringing the nascent policy landscape to scholars' desks, explaining and discussing with them how it will affect their working conditions and informing them about their options when deciding on dissemination strategies for their research is a central part of our Open Science activities. This is an activity that faces both upward, to make policy-makers aware of our community's distinct requirements, and downwards, to support arts and humanities researchers as they respond to policy changes.

In 2018, the boldest move in the European open policy landscape was clearly the launch of Plan S, expressing the collective will of 11 national science funders in making full and immediate Open Access to research

publications a reality. Plan S requires indeed that, from 2020, scientific publications that result from research funded by public grants must be published in compliant Open Access journals or platforms. Having a strong potential to transform and define the future of scholarly communication in Europe, the plan has sparked intense debates from the moment of its release. DARIAH joined this discussion in its early phase and published a Position Paper that adds the perspective of arts and humanities researchers and disciplines to this dialogue and made recommendations to facilitate the inclusive and optimal implementation of the plan. Publishing the paper also gave us the opportunity to intensify the conversation with and within the arts and humanities communities around DARIAH about scholarly communication in general and Open Access in particular.

Aurélien Berra
 @aurelberra

Suivre

So many good points in this contribution by @DARIAHeu. Well done! #OpenAccess #planS

George Macgregor
 @g3om4c

Suivre

This. @DARIAHeu position on #PlanS. Published prior to implementation guidance but highlights (my growing) concerns with the approach. Disenfranchisement of scholars without rethink.

punctum books
 @punctum_books

Suivre

Important position statement from @DARIAHeu on #Plan_S representing their constituency of Arts and Humanities researchers. #OpenAccess

UniWestPress
 @UniWestPress

Suivre

Much to agree with @DARIAHeu 's response to #PlanS
 Necessary points to be made on behalf of social sciences & especially #humanities which university presses care about!
bit.ly/2RBdEs1

Extract attached but much more useful said.

In 2018, we also prepared two guideline documents to support humanities scholars who are taking their first, second or even further steps towards opening up their research. *Open Data for Humanists, A Practical Guide*, as the title implies, builds a bridge between the rhetoric of Open Science (which emerged from, and remains strongly influenced by, the practices and conditions of work in the hard sciences) and the methods and source landscape of the humanities.

The Open Access guidelines for the arts and humanities: recommendations by DARIAH consist of two components: a value statement describing what we recognize as viable and sustainable models of Open Access in an arts and humanities context, and a toolkit that can be directly and easily included in the publishing workflows of our communities to achieve compliance with the evolving Open Access mandates in Europe.

d. Fostering projects to help the communities grow

i. The DARIAH Theme 2017-18: Cultural Heritage and Humanities Research: Evaluation and impact

With a focus on the topic of *Cultural Heritage and Humanities Research*, the 2017-18 edition of the DARIAH Theme project funding aimed at exploring the possible working relationships between cultural heritage institutions and researchers in the arts and humanities, focusing on the requirements and commitments that would facilitate the exchange of cultural heritage information.

The funded projects delivered 7 substantive events across Europe, engaging in total around 150 researchers. The following conferences, workshops or more interactive events such as hackathons were organised:

- *Persée up* hackathon: problems and innovative answers when navigating and consulting a digital library (Ecole Normale Supérieure de Lyon, France).
- A DARIAH Connectivity Day on the topic of *Digital Infrastructures for Digital Cultural Heritage and Media Art Research* within the context of the 7th International Re:Trace Conference for Histories of Media Art, Science and Technology (Danube University Krems, Austria).
- A hands-on workshop on the topic of *Promoting Digital Research Methods and Academic Re-use of the Digital Heritage content in the European Academic Community* (Polish Academy of Sciences, Poland).
- A cross-domain and collaborative workshop on *Opening Data in Heritage Science* to set the context for data opening and re-use across Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage (DARIAH Italy).
- A symposium and workshop *Archives that Matter* inviting artists and researchers across geographies and academic disciplines to explore and critically engage with the colonial archival records (Uncertain Archives Research Group, University of Copenhagen, Denmark).
- Four workshops in the frame of the project *Cooperation Framework of Digital Infrastructure in the Region (CFDI) – Opportunities and Needs in Case of Material Concerning Famous People in Science and Culture* to initiate cooperation between different GLAM institutions of the wider region of Zagreb (Croatian Academy of Sciences and Arts, Croatia).
- A two-day conference including presentations and practical workshops on the topic of *Making Cultural Heritage Data Accessible and Reusable: Finding Best Practices* organised by DARIAH-PL, DARIAH-DE and the Polish History Museum to foster cooperation regarding the re-use of digital heritage resources in academic research in the field of humanities (Poland).

Focus on the DARIAH Theme project: Making Cultural Heritage Data Accessible and Reusable: Finding Best Practices

Making Cultural Heritage Data Accessible and Reusable: Finding Best Practices was a conference organised by the Polish and German chapters of DARIAH (DARIAH-PL, DARIAH-DE) in conjunction with the Polish History Museum. The event took place from 19-20 April at the University of Warsaw.

The event was a continuation of a series of workshops on *Public Humanities and Digital Humanities: Mutual Inspiration and Common (Digital) Tools*, organised by DARIAH-PL and the Coalition for Open Education as part of the *DARIAH Theme 2016 Public Humanities* funding scheme. These workshops underlined the need for close cooperation between researchers and heritage institutions and helped to identify main barriers for such cooperation.

The first day of the event was designed as a forum with speakers selected through an open call to the GLAM sector and Cultural Heritage institutions. In addition, there were invited presentations by institutions with long experience in the field, among them the National Institute for Museums and Public Collections, the National Heritage Board of Poland, the National Digital Archives and the National Museum in Warsaw. The mixture of speakers shaped a good overview of the field and set the stage for the two more practical workshops that followed on the second day.

The first workshop concerned technical aspects of cooperation between researchers and the GLAM sector, including standards, data exchange protocols, API usage and sharing of digital objects. The second workshop was dedicated to legal aspects of sharing and using of digital resources. The main goal of the workshops was to develop recommendations for cultural and heritage institutions and researchers willing to carry out joint projects.

Materials collected during the workshops are currently being edited and will soon be published.

Focus on the DARIAH Theme project: Archives that Matter

2017 marked the centennial for Denmark's selling of former colonial territories, the Danish West Indies, known today as US Virgin Islands, to the United States. To mark this occasion, the Danish National Archive, the Royal Danish Library's Photo and Map Collection along with other archives and collections in Denmark, undertook a mass-digitisation of their archival records from St. Croix, St. Thomas, St. John, Ghana and the transatlantic enslavement trade. From January 30 to February 9 2018, the Uncertain Archives Research Group organised and held a symposium and workshop, inviting artists and researchers across geographies and academic disciplines to explore, confront and critically engage with the colonial archival records.

The symposium was attended by more than 70 people from various disciplines and backgrounds, while the ensuing workshop was attended by 20 people. The symposium and workshop facilitated a necessary and complex debate around the ethical, aesthetic and political dimensions of the digitisation of the colonial archives and paved the road for new ways of designing a trans-locational digital platform for accessing, sharing and disseminating colonial archival material in the future.

ii. WG Funding Scheme 2017-18

In August 2017, DARIAH launched its first ever call for funding proposals from the Working Groups. The funding allocated under this scheme was intended to support the activities of the established DARIAH Working Groups, by offering them practical support for their programmes, encouraging innovative ideas, building up capacity to suggest new services or help develop and sustain existing ones.

In response to the call, we provided funding to **12 WG projects** taking place between October 2017 to the end of October 2018. The nature of the projects covered a wide range of activities and outputs, including workshops, meetings, reports, internships, and software development, all of which made significant contributions to the effectiveness and reach of our Working Groups.

- WG Digital Methods and Practices Observatory: *Digital humanities work in focus: multiple case studies of research projects across Europe*
- WG Sustainable Publishing of (meta)data: *Trust and Understanding: the value of metadata in a digitally joined-up world*
- WG Lexical Resources: *Sustaining TEI-Lex*
- WG Image Science and Media Art Research: *DARIAH Digital Art, Science, and Technology Institution Network (DARIAH-DASTIN)*
- WG Federated Identity Management for DARIAH: *2nd DARIAH AAI Service Provider Workshop*
- WG Impact Factors and Success Criteria: *Measuring Change in DH: Workshop on Impact Factors and Success Criteria*
- WG Thesaurus Maintenance: *Setting up e-infrastructure for collaborative work on thesaurus integration*
- WG DH Course Registry: *Metadata-thon: taking the DH Course Registry to the next level*
- WG Ethics and Legality in the Digital Arts and Humanities: *Open Licensing, Ethics and Scholarly Conduct in DH*
- WG Text and Data Analytics: *DARIAH Workshop on Distant Reading in Literary Texts*
- WG Women in History: *A new NEWW tool: trying, testing, teaching*
- WG Community Engagement: *Engaging Research Communities Beyond DARIAH*

Featured event: Trust and Understanding: the value of metadata in a digitally joined-up world

The **Sustainable Publishing of (Meta)data Working Group**, chaired by Afelonne Doek, Dorien Styven, Eric de Ruijter and Johan Van Der Eycken, received funding to organise a workshop on the topic of *Trust and Understanding: the value of metadata in a digitally joined-up world*.

This workshop took place on 14 and 15 May 2018 at the National Archives of Belgium in Brussels, with 64 people attending from different scientific institutions, universities and funding institutions (including the **FWO – Scientific Research Foundation Flanders**). Issues regarding (meta)data were addressed from different viewpoints, towards implementing an integrated approach encompassing both technical and practical aspects of (meta)data: Metadata, a path to standardisation; Metadata and Society; Metadata communication and interoperability.

Through this workshop, the Working Group was able to share knowledge, know-how and tools within the DARIAH community and offer answers to questions arising in the dialogue between the archival sector and its users, in particular arts and humanities researchers. A second outcome was the improvement of cooperation within **DARIAH-BE** through a specific project. Cooperation between the entities **DARIAH-VL, DARIAH-FWB and DARIAH-FED** is complicated due to the federalised state structure in Belgium and the separate financing of these entities. Through this workshop, the Working Group was able to move beyond these barriers resulting, for example, in a collaborative Belgian (Open) Science Cloud bringing together **CESSDA** and DARIAH. The Working Group funding also supported – in an extension of the workshop – the project *Awareness: understanding and having fun, fostering communities around the Standardisation Survival Kit* bringing together the Working Group network and the PARTHENOS project team. A final result of the workshop was the expansion of the Working Group with additional members from the museum sector (**KIK-IRPA, BOZAR, KU Leuven**).

A summary of the results of the workshop are available on the website of the **State Archives of Belgium**, and will appear in **ABB. Tijdschrift voor Archief – en Bibliotheekwezen** Journal as peer-reviewed articles in 2019.

Open Licensing, Ethics and Scholarly Conduct in DH

The **Ethics and Legality in the Digital Arts and Humanities (ELDAH) Working Group**, chaired by Koraljka Kuzman Šlogar, Walter Scholger and Vanessa Hanneschläger, received funding to develop the project *Open Licensing, Ethics and Scholarly Conduct in DH*.

The Working Group noted that there is a recognisable political drive in the European Union to facilitate free and public access to cultural heritage and research data hosted at publicly funded institutions.

More recently, the new EU regulation on Data Protection (GDPR) caused a lot of insecurity and, due to the lack of clear advice, prompted frantic activity that often went beyond actual legal requirements. ELDAH aimed to tackle these issues by providing reliable information for humanities scholars facing such legal questions and uncertainties in their research, not from a legalist but from a community- and practice-oriented perspective.

To this purpose, the Working Group developed, provided and shared some concrete recommendations by and for developers and scholars. The findings and results of this work were disseminated at eight conferences and workshops, via websites and the HAL repository, but also as training materials and recommendations for open licensing of research data and results. The Working Group funding allowed three face-to-face meetings to be organised, with integrated workshops for developing a work plan and roadmap for the Working Group, assigning tasks to individual members and designing surveys for the community, among other activities. Additionally, ELDAH was able to establish collaborations with similar groups within the large European research infrastructures who are also developing recommendations that will transcend national or infrastructural boundaries: with the **Legal and Ethical Issues Committee of CLARIN ERIC (CLIC)**, the **Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA)** and the **Europeana Networks Association**, as well as pertinent working groups of national organisations: the **Open Science Network Austria (OANA)** and the Association for Digital Humanities in German speaking Countries (DHd).

Finally, the Working Group invested in raising its profile, designing a new logo and developing other promotional material (postcards, bookmarks, flyers) with messages and content related to ethical and legal issues and how-to licensing guidelines.

WG ELDAH meeting and workshop in Zagreb, October 2018. From the left: Miha Seručnik, Vlatka Lemić, Irena Miholić, Jasenka Ferber Bogdan, Simon Gabay, Iva Melinščak Zlodi, Walter Scholger, Vanessa Hanneschläger, Koraljka Kuzman Šlogar, Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra, Jelena Mihnjak, Marianne Ping Huang, Pavel Straňák, Erik Ketzan. Photo: Matia Mikulčić.

3. Doing things right and doing the right things

a. Changes in the Organisation

2018 saw many changes in the DARIAH team. As a lively and vibrant network, it evolved and developed by attracting new members and adding new expertise in several DARIAH bodies. These changes contributed to strengthen the knowledge capacities of the network and better representing arts and humanities communities with a stronger voice in the different fora.

2018 saw a new President of the Board of Directors, Jennifer Edmond, succeeding Laurent Romary, and a new Director joining the Board, Toma Tasovac.

The Scientific Board saw two of its members withdrawing, Andrew Prescott (University of Glasgow) and Manfred Thaller (University of Cologne), and welcomed two new members Sarah Kenderdine, (Professor of Digital Museology at the École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL)), and Arianna Betti, (Professor (Chair) of Philosophy of Language at the University of Amsterdam).

The DARIAH Coordination Office also witnessed some changes. Mike Mertens, CEO of DARIAH, was succeeded by Arnaud Roi as Secretary General while a new Outreach and Communications Officer joined the team, Eliza Papaki. Also, for the first time an Open Science Officer joined the DARIAH Coordination Office, Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra, filling a very important gap by approaching the topic of Open Science from the humanities perspective. With Mike Mertens and Jakob Epler leaving, the DARIAH Coordination Office in Göttingen closed its doors but a new one was opened in Dublin, at Trinity College where Jennifer Edmond and Eliza Papaki have their offices.

These various appointments also led in some cases to further internal changes as well, with Sally Chambers being elected as Chair of the National Coordinators Committee, succeeding Toma Tasovac, and Nicolas Larousse elected as Vice Chair of the Committee.

We believe that each person brings a different perspective, expertise and dynamic to the DARIAH network. We therefore welcome the new people and roles on board and work towards tuning this activity to the constantly evolving needs of our community.

b. Developing a Strategic Plan for DARIAH

The DARIAH team commenced its work for the year with a second iteration of the *Strategy Days* event, first held in 2017. This event saw the 20 members of the DARIAH Board, Senior Management Team, Coordination Office and Joint Research Committee come together in Berlin for a three-day meeting.

The agenda for the meeting was constructed around 4 key pillars: a review of key actions undertaken in the previous year, an investigation of the DARIAH identity, a revision of the organisational structures for knowledge management and a final session focussing on how we engage with our environment, and in particular with our research communities.

The strategic meeting began with an exercise in defining the DARIAH 'brand' by comparing DARIAH to a number of organisations it is not, namely: CLARIN, EADH, EASSH, EGI and Europeana. This discussion was followed by a series of exercises facilitated by an external agency: *Undivided*: How could you draw DARIAH as a picture? If you were to reinvent DARIAH, what 3 things would you leave, take and add? What Jungian archetype best describes DARIAH? Finally, how will people in the future complete the sentence: 'DARIAH did X so that Y happened'?

From these exercises we were able to confirm the many different ways in which DARIAH and its value are seen, but also that there are some key points of consensus: DARIAH's people and knowledge are valued as a strength, but its organisation is not always felt to be fit to purpose and lacks transparency. As for things we would add, confidence, better communications and a clear value proposition all resonated with the group.

Strategy Days 2018, Berlin, Germany, January 2018

Our second major session addressed the issues of knowledge management within the organisation. Our conclusions from this very active discussion were clear: DARIAH needs to become more professional and more effective about its knowledge management, we need to think not just about communication through documents, but how we build, maintain and share institutional memory.

In our final session, we discussed the environment in which DARIAH operates, and how we might optimise this engagement. We developed together a list of the types of organisations with which we should or could engage, from which the research communities were deemed to be both challenging and central. We also came to a tentative conclusion that DARIAH's strategic focus going forward must be on providing tangible services to the community, and that the four clear areas around which these services are being built are as follows: the Marketplace (for tools, services, and data), the Working Groups (for knowledge and sharing of practice transnationally), Training and Education (to enable adoption of the digital) and Policy Work (to ensure a receptive environment for our communities' needs).

The discussions and conclusions from this event proved an excellent foundation for the creation of DARIAH's first ever Strategic Plan. An initial draft of this document was circulated internally in August, and refined over the course of the rest of the year. After much editing and consultation among all of the layers and bodies of DARIAH, the plan will be formally submitted to the General Assembly for acceptance as policy in May 2019. The final document refines the conclusions of the Strategy Days, but also adds significant material to guide DARIAH's development, including a plan for measuring our success according to quantitative and qualitative measures, a set of categories to guide our conceptualisation of the impact we make, and revised expressions of the DARIAH Vision, Mission and Values. Pulling all of this together has been a significant focus of our efforts in 2018 and early 2019, which we feel will pay off in the future by bringing us a basis according to which we focus our activities and understand the difference they make.

Strategy Days 2018

c. Implementation of the DARIAH Contributions Tool

The in-kind contributions made by DARIAH members to the central infrastructure are one of the most distinctive and powerful assets in our infrastructural model. Collecting, validating and promoting the reuse of these contributions is not always a straightforward matter, however. For this reason, the Humanities at Scale project was charged with the development of a Contributions Management Tool to administer and monitor the contributions, facilitate their quality control and ease their later reuse by the community. Since March 2018, DARIAH's CIO team has taken up the challenge to implement the newly designed workflows and the corresponding tool.

In 2018, training sessions were organised for all National Coordinators, the individuals responsible for submitting the contributions, as well as with the JRC members who act as the contribution reviewers. In addition, detailed feedback was collected on the entire process which will be incorporated in the (online) documentation of the tool. The feedback will also form part of the evaluation report produced to be at the end of the implementation phase (August 2019).

By the end of 2018, a total of 254 contributions had been submitted, reporting on the financial year 2017. The finalization of the reviews is envisioned for April 2019, after which the year 2017 can be closed off and the contributions made live as reusable tools, services and knowledge in the DARIAH ecosystem.

d. Planning the Marketplace

The future Marketplace is one of the pillars of DARIAH. Plainly stated, it will function as a discovery platform for humanities data, tools and workflows. Since DARIAH's inception, a lot of effort has gone into organising the digital landscape, mostly in the shape of registries for tools and services. Sustainability has proven to be a problem, not only technically, but also socially. How do we make sure a platform is accepted and valued by the community? In 2018, we studied prior attempts at building such platforms, within and beyond DARIAH. We are now in a position to learn from past projects and pave the way forward to provide a sustainable discovery environment in service of humanities scholars.

The Marketplace is strongly related to our endeavours to connect our communities to the emerging European Open Science Cloud. Together with our SSH partner infrastructures, such as CLARIN, SHARE, ESS and CESSDA, we successfully worked on a larger proposal, which yielded the SSHOC project (Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud) starting in January 2019 and running for 40 months.

DARIAH is involved on many levels of the project, but most of our work will be dedicated to Work Package 7, which we lead, and which is specifically dedicated to the Marketplace. So we have the means at hand to master our task.

e. Fostering better communications within the network

Over the course of 2018, DARIAH refined many aspects of its operations, including a significant renewal of its outreach and communications functions. Fostering a good level of information exchange within and outside of a network, with the size and complexity of DARIAH, will always be a challenge, in particular considering our distributed nature and wide range of stakeholders across disciplines, sectors, languages and countries. Under the new leadership of Outreach and Communications Officer Eliza Papaki, DARIAH was able to begin in 2018 to address a number of long-standing communications issues, and make significant progress in streamlining information flows. Particular challenges addressed in 2018 have included developing better channels of communication with the DARIAH national members and in particular Cooperating Partners, establishing a network of national contact points for communication and dissemination, and mapping the DARIAH user audience to develop a better understanding of their various needs. All these activities and initiatives had a dual goal: to sustain on the one hand a good communication level for DARIAH, to rethink and innovate on the other hand and foster a more well-connected network.

4. Looking Ahead

2018 has been a year in which a number of key processes have commenced: we look forward to seeing them come to fruition in 2019 and beyond. With the launch of our Strategic Plan in May, we will make a formal and public commitment to our development trajectory, in line with the input of our many stakeholders. In addition, the commencement of the real work of the SSHOC project will see us progress the development of the DARIAH SSH Marketplace. Our work in 2019 will be defined by the design of the data model, which needs to ensure interoperability, and a workflow for community-driven population of the resource, an element which will be a key driver of the Marketplace's social sustainability. We also look forward to our third and final international DARIAH beyond Europe event, which will take place in March 2019 in Canberra, Australia.

In addition to these headline strategic achievements already in development for 2019, we also look forward to seeing some of our operational improvements take hold and further improve the organisation. Communications, policy work and the collection of in-kind contributions have all been overhauled in 2018, but the real impact of these changes will only be felt in 2019 and beyond. Furthermore, we look forward to developing a second Strategic Action Plan, sharpening our work in Training and Education and implementing an organisation-wide programme to collect data to feed our new 'User Barometer,' a snapshot view of who is accessing our services and how.

We foresee all of these activities as avenues by which to keep the DARIAH community vibrant and strong, building upon the significant successes of 2018 toward the goal of providing an ever more essential set of infrastructural services for the arts and humanities in the digital age.

Appendix I: Administrative and Legal Details

Who's who in DARIAH

Body: Board of Directors

Role: The Board of Directors is the executive body of DARIAH and its legal representative. It is composed of three directors, appointed by the General Assembly. The BoD provides leadership, represents DARIAH, shapes strategy and controls the performance and is responsible for the day-to-day operations, in support by the DARIAH Coordination Office.

People

Name		Role in DARIAH	Affiliation
	Jennifer Edmond	President, Board of Directors	Trinity College Dublin
	Frank Fischer	Director, Board of Directors	Higher School of Economics, Moscow
	Toma Tasovac	Director, Board of Directors	Belgrade Center for Digital Humanities

Body: Scientific Board

Role: The Scientific Board advises DARIAH, via the General Assembly, on specific issues, such as the future research landscape and technological innovation. Its members are arts and humanities researchers with international reputation in the field and therefore significant experience in digitally enabled research methods.

People

Name	Role in DARIAH / Affiliation	
	Riccardo Pozzo	Chair of the Scientific Board/Università di Verona
	Sarah Kenderdine	École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL)
	Roxane Wyns	LIBIS
	Jan Rybicki	Jagiellonian University
	Sonja de Leeuw	Utrecht University
	Patrik Svensson	UCLA
	Jane Ohlmeyer	Trinity College, Dublin
	Chad Gaffield	University of Ottawa
	Francis Prost	University Paris 1 -Panthéon Sorbonne/CNRS/French Ministry of Higher Education and Research
	Arianna Betti	University of Amsterdam

Body: DARIAH Coordination Office

Role: The daily work of DARIAH is undertaken by the DCO; headed by the Secretary General, assisted by the Chief Organisation Officer, it is responsible for financial, legal, coordination and communications operations in respect of all the above bodies for the effective running of the ERIC. It has distributed operations and offices in France (Paris), Germany (Berlin), Ireland (Dublin) and the Netherlands (The Hague).

People

Name		Role in DARIAH
	Arnaud Roi	Secretary General
	Anne Grésillon	Chief Organisation Officer
	Suzanne Dumouchel	Partnerships and Public Affairs Officer
	Marco Raciti	European Project Manager
	Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra	Open Science Officer
	Yoann Moranville	Developer and Research Associate
	Eliza Papaki	Outreach and Communications Officer
	Andrea Scharnhorst	Chief Integration Officer
	Francesca Morselli	Integration Officer
	Femmy Admiraal	Integration Officer

Body: National Coordinators Committee

Role: Each DARIAH member country has its own National Coordinator, who oversees DARIAH activities in his or her country on behalf of its national membership consortium. These activities are the setting up of a national roadmap for the digitally enabled arts and humanities, and coordinating the submission of in-kind contributions, such as the tools, services, software, collections, expertise and researcher networks that are established as a result of implementing the respective national roadmap. The NCC meets regularly to integrate national DARIAH activities at the European level.

People

Name	Role in DARIAH / Country	Affiliation
Sally Chambers	Chair of the National Coordinators Committee	Ghent Centre for Digital Humanities
Nicolas Larousse	Vice Chair of the National Coordinators Committee	Huma-Num
Emiliano Degl'Innocenti	Italy	Italian Council of Research
Mörth Karlheinz	Austria	Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities, Austrian Academy of Sciences
Marinos Ioannides	Cyprus	Cyprus University of Technology
Birte Christensen-Dalsgaard	Denmark	Digital Humanities Lab Denmark
Stéphane Pouyllau	France	Huma-Num
Mirjam Blümm	Germany	State and University Library Göttingen
Koraljka Kuzman Šlogar	Croatia	Archive, Institute of Ethnology and Folklore Research
Andreas Fickers	Luxembourg	Luxembourg Centre for Contemporary and Digital History
Jurij Hadalin	Slovenia	Institute of Contemporary History/ Primorska University
Maria Spiliotopoulou	Greece	Academy of Athens
Orla Murphy	Ireland	University College Cork
Gertjan Filarski	Netherlands	KNAW – Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences

Body: Joint Research Committee

Role: The JRC organises the integration of DARIAH's technical developments and innovation activities. It is chaired by DARIAH's Chief Integration Officer (CIO) and consists of the Heads of each of DARIAH's Virtual Competency Centres.

People

Name	Role in DARIAH	Affiliation
Andrea Scharnhorst	Chief Integration Officer	DARIAH/DANS
Tibor Kálmán	Heads of VCC1	GWDC
Matej Durco		ACDH-OeAW
Agiatis Benardou	Heads of VCC2	Digital Curation Unit, ATHENA R.C.
Marianne Ping Huang		Aarhus University
Nicolas Larrousse	Heads of VCC3	Huma-Num
Marcin Werla		Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center
Fabio Cotti	Heads of VCC4	University of Roma Tor Vergata
Dirk Wintergrün		Max Planck Institute for the History of Science

Appendix II: Finances

In 2018, DARIAH took an important step towards more transparency and accuracy by contracting the expertise of an auditor and an accountant. The accounting and auditing procedures focused first on the fiscal years 2014, 2015, 2016 and 2017. The auditor concluded that DARIAH's financial statements "give a true and fair view of the assets and liabilities and of the financial position and of the net assets of its operation according to the French accounting principles." After this necessary catch-up, DARIAH's finances will be, from now on, audited every year according to the French law, where DARIAH has its statutory seat. It is to be noted that the finances 2018 presented in this report have not been audited yet, since the General Assembly will only meet in November 2018 to validate the accounts. However, DARIAH is in position to give an accurate situation of the 2018 finances that reflect DARIAH's operations in an understandable manner for our stakeholders.

DARIAH ERIC consists of 17 member countries that contribute to its budget in two different ways: through cash contributions and in-kind contributions. In 2018, according to the budget voted by the General Assembly, the contributions from the member countries amount to:

2018 Cash contribution:	696.586 €
2018 In-kind contribution:	4.163.034 €
DARIAH balance 2017	486.503 €
DARIAH income 2018	707.628 €
DARIAH expenses 2018	753.735 €
Balance 2018	- 46.108 €
Total balance	440.396 €

Resources:

Due to their very nature, the in-kind contributions are not included in the calculation of resources available to run DARIAH's operations. The total income 2018 is mostly composed of cash contributions and diverse reimbursements, such as healthcare insurance repayments or refund for overpayment.

Operating expenses:

The largest component of operating expenses is by far the personnel costs which represents 70% of the total costs. The operation costs for the year 2018 is distributed as follows:

Type of costs	2018	2017
Staff Costs	515.519 €	513.049 €
Project Funding (Community And Working Groups)	64.174 €	58.748 €
Travel & Hotel	56.674 €	44.881 €
Development In-Kind Contribution Tool	33.000 €	-€
Event Organization	20.590 €	57.569 €
Accounting & Audit	20.079 €	-€
Communication	17.928 €	34.442 €
Catering	11.605 €	5.292 €
Consulting	6.177 €	-€
Consumables	3.061 €	7.714 €
Bank Charges	2.842 €	6.095 €
Conference/ Membership Fee	1.460 €	1.016 €
Training	375 €	-€
Petty Cash	250 €	200 €
Total	753.735 €	729.006 €

European projects

European projects funding is solely used to carry out specific projects in which DARIAH is involved in:

- Humanities at Scale: Evolving the DARIAH-ERIC (HaS-DARIAH), Grant agreement number 675570. Although the project ended on December 31, 2017 some costs actually occurred at the beginning of 2018.
- DARIAH ERIC Sustainability Refined (DESIR), Grant agreement number 731081.
- Pooling Activities, Resources and Tools for Heritage E-research Networking, Optimisation and Synergies (PARTHENOS), Grant agreement number 65419.
- High Integration of Research Monographs in the European Open Science infrastructure (HIRMEOS), Grant agreement number 731102.
- OpenAIRE Advancing Open Scholarship (OpenAIRE-Advance), Grant agreement number 777541.
- The European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science Preparatory Phase (E-RIHS PP), Grant agreement number 739503.

	Income	Expenses
HaS-DARIAH	15.663 €	15.663 €
DESIR	148.110 €	148.110 €
PARTHENOS	10.316 €	10.316 €
HIRMEOS	16.351 €	16.351 €
OpenAIRE-Advance	5.000 €	5.000 €
E-RIHS PP	26.630 €	26.630 €
Total European projects	222.069 €	222.069 €

Other project

DARIAH received in 2018 a total of 50.000€, 25.000€ from the French Ministry of Higher Education, Research and Innovation (MESRI) and 25.000€ from the German Ministry of Higher Education and Research (BMBF), to organise specific events, such as the Lexical Data Masterclass that took place in December 2018.

	Income	Expenses
Lexical Data Masterclass 2018	50.000 €	12.587 €* 2018

*more expenses occurred in 2019

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